

Surgery for Compressive Pericardial Effusion

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Compressive pericardial effusion is a life-threatening emergency, and its etiologies are varied. Ultrasound confirms the diagnosis. Surgical drainage allows both evacuation of the effusion and the performance of a pericardial biopsy for etiological purposes.

Objective: The main objective of this study is to evaluate the epidemiological profile of compressive pericardial effusions, to specify their etiologies, and to analyze the results of surgery.

Patients and methods: This retrospective study includes all consecutive files of patients in the cardiovascular surgery department of Gafsa Hospital between January 1, 2015, and December 31, 2022, for the management of cardiac tamponade. Minimal and asymptomatic pericardial effusions were excluded.

Results: A total of 45 patients (25 women and 20 men) were operated on for compressive pericardial effusion. The average age of our patients was 53.7 ± 15.4 years. Dyspnea was the most frequent reason for consultation (71.1%). Cardiac ultrasound allowed diagnosis in all patients. Treatment was surgical in all patients. The fluid was sero-hematic without 62.2%. Tuberculous origin was observed in 5 cases (11.1%), neoplastic in 6 cases (13.3%), and non-specific inflammation in 34 cases (75.6%).

Conclusion: Surgery for compressive pericardial effusions is the “Gold Standard”, it allows both drainage and performance of a pericardial biopsy.

Keywords: Compressive pericardial effusion; Cardiac Ultrasound ; Surgery

INTRODUCTION

Compressive pericardial effusion is caused by an abnormal increase in fluid accumulation in the pericardial sac which, by increasing intracardiac pressure, impairs normal cardiac filling and reduces cardiac output.^[1]

Clinical manifestations of pericardial effusion include pulsus paradoxus, tachycardia, increased jugular venous pressure, and hypotension. Echocardiography allows confirmation of the diagnosis and a precise assessment of its hemodynamic impact.^[2]

The causes of compressive pericardial effusion are numerous as it is a potential complication of any of several

pericardial disease processes, including infectious, inflammatory, traumatic, and malignant etiologies.^[1,3]

Therapeutic indication and timing of intervention should take into account the clinical presentation and echocardiographic findings, as well as a careful assessment of risks and benefits for each patient.^[4]

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This is a retrospective study extended over a period of 8 years, between January 2015 and December 2022, on 45 patients presenting with compressive pericardial effusion, and having been treated within the cardiovascular surgery department of the Gafsa regional hospital.

All data used in our work were collected from the patient files of the cardiovascular surgery department of the Gafsa regional hospital. Asymptomatic and minimal pericardial effusions were excluded.

The collection of data in medical files was done in ascending chronological order from January 2015 to December 2022, using operating records.

For the statistical study, we reported all the data on an Excel table and we used the SPSS 23 software. The qualitative variables of our study were expressed in percentage and in number, while the quantitative variables in means +/- deviations standards.

RESULTS

We operated on 45 patients during the period from January 2015 to December 2022. The average age of our patients was 53.7 ± 15.4 years (Figure 1). In this study we identified 20 men and 25 women.

The reasons for consultation were (Figure 2):

- Isolated chest pain in 4 patients (8.9%).
- Isolated dyspnea in 32 patients (71.1%).
- Chest pain associated with dyspnea in 9 patients (20%).

Forty-one patients had dyspnea (91.1%), six were stage II, thirty-one stage III and four were stage IV (Figure 3).

All patients had tachycardia and thirty-five patients had right signs (turgor of the jugulars, edema of the lower limbs).

Chest x-ray showed (Figure 4):

- Cardiomegaly in all patients with a jug heart in 18 cases (40%).
- Bilateral pleural effusion in 6 cases (13.3%).
- Pulmonary opacity in 2 cases (4.4%).

Echocardiographic data were available in all patients. The effusion was abundant in 100% of cases (> 20 mm) (Figure 5).

All patients were operated on via the Marfan subxiphoid approach.

The appearance of the fluid was sero-hematic in 28 cases (62.2%), purulent in 1 case (2.2%), and citrine in 16 cases (35.6%). The average drainage amount was 722.2 ± 240 ml.

A systematic pericardial biopsy carried out for anatomical-pathological examination revealed pericarditis of tuberculous origin in 5 cases (11.1%), acute neoplastic pericarditis in 6 cases (13.3%) and non-specific

inflammation. in 34 cases (75.6%) (Figure 6).

The average length of hospital stay was 6.31 ± 1.78 days.

The surgical outcomes were favorable in 44 cases. One death occurred intraoperatively; it was in fact a type A aortic dissection ruptured in the pericardium.

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to age group

Figure 2: Distribution of patients according to reason for consultation

Figure 3: Distribution of patients according to stage of dyspnea

Figure 4: Heart in carafe

Figure 5: Cardiac ultrasound showing pericardial effusion

Figure 6: Etiologies of compressive pericarditis

DISCUSSION

In our study, the mean age of our patients was 53.7 ± 15.4 years. The age groups most affected were 40 to 60 years old in 44.4% of cases.

Our results are close to those of Aubert et al^[5] in France who reported in their study a mean age of 53 ± 17 years.

Our sample was made up of 55.5% female versus 44.6% male. The sex ratio (M/F) was 0.8. This result is identical to that of the literature data.^[6,7]

The reason for consultation was dyspnea in 71.1%. Elsewhere, chest pain was the most frequent reason for

consultation in the study carried out by Gribaa et al^[8] 72.7%.

Chest radiography was performed in all our patients; 100% of patients had radiological cardiomegaly with a cardiothoracic index greater than 0.5. Our results are superimposable to those of Bouakez et al^[9] who found a predominance of cardiomegaly.

Echocardiography currently appears to be the most effective non-bloody method for diagnosis. In fact, it makes it possible to assess the abundance of the effusion, to detect signs of compression of the right cardiac chambers and to look for signs of pericardial constriction. Furthermore, it allows us to add etiological arguments which remain the main problem.^[9]

All our patients underwent cardiac ultrasound to confirm the positive diagnosis and to assess hemodynamic tolerance. Pericardial effusion was abundant in 100% of cases.

Camposet al^[10] reported in their series of 59 patients, a predominance of very abundant pericardial tissue with associated signs of tamponade (83% of cases).

A systematic pericardial biopsy carried out for anatomical-pathological examination revealed pericarditis of tuberculous origin in 5 cases (11.1%), acute neoplastic pericarditis in 6 cases (13.3%) and non-specific inflammation. in 34 cases (75.6%).

Concerning the etiologies found, the literature data^[10-13] agree to find approximately 20% of etiological diagnoses in unselected populations, without invasive examinations, and up to 80% in so-called populations. at risk.^[14,15] In our investigation, coordinated care between cardiologists and cardiovascular surgeons, with a minimal standardized etiological assessment then adapted to clinical presumptions, made it possible to find 7 proven etiologies of pericarditis, or 27% of etiological diagnoses, which seems close to the literature without invasive examinations.

The treatment of acute pericarditis complicated by pericardial effusion initially remains medical.^[16] It sometimes requires emergency pericardial drainage via a surgical or percutaneous approach when the acute pericarditis is symptomatic or frankly compressive with a picture of cardiac tamponade. The indications remain controversial, especially in the face of low abundance and well tolerated effusion.^[17] The aim of approaching the pericardium is to evacuate the effusion, eliminate compression and, possibly, aid in the diagnosis of this effusion by analyzing the fluid and pericardial fragments obtained by biopsy.^[18] The subxiphoid surgical approach used since the 19th century was our preference due to its simplicity and ease of execution.^[19]

According to Gumrukcuoglu^[20] and Becit^[21], this approach makes it possible to effectively wash the pericardial cavity, especially if the fluid is purulent, and has the advantage of allowing biopsies to be carried out unlike pericardial puncture. . It is also favored by other authors over thoracotomy which causes respiratory complications.^[22,23] Unlike thoracotomy, the subxiphoid route does not allow pericardiectomies to be performed.^[24]

Furthermore, although the subxiphoid approach is more invasive than pericardiocentesis, it only allows inspection of a small part of the pericardium or even the wall of the right ventricle. But this route has another advantage which is that it can be carried out under local anesthesia; what we achieved in two patients presenting a precarious general condition.

The biopsy of the pericardium made it possible, in our study, to make the etiological diagnosis dominated by non-specific inflammations after the anatomo-pathological examination. No patient experienced a recurrence, which

could have pointed to primary pericardial mesothelioma, a rare tumor pathology.^[25]

CONCLUSION

Compressive pericardial effusions result from “wet” pericarditis with a large volume of effusion or from a pericardial effusion that develops very quickly. Although pericardiocentesis constitutes an advantageous technique, in hemodynamically unstable patients, surgical drainage is the “gold standard”, especially in a peripheral hospital.

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